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EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT: A DRIVER OF ORGANIZATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS

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Abstract

Employee engagement is a key business driver for organizational success. In a world that is changing both in terms of the global nature of work and the diversity of the workforce, engaged employees may be a key to competitive advantage. Companies that understand the conditions that enhance employee engagement will have accomplished something that Competitors will find very difficult to imitate, and the purpose of this research is to find out the degree of employees' perception on employee engagement in engineering industry, Vijayawada. And to analyze the factors which are predominant in influencing the employees positively towards employee engagement.

The opinions of employees are collected by a standard questionnaire of Gallup's study on employee engagement. Apart from demographic analysis, the reliability of sample was tested by using Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy and the factor analysis was conducted, the results shows that conducive work

environment, optimistic attitude, effective supervisor, core values, organizational relationship, and career development are indispensable to motivate the employee engagement, implications are discussed and recommendations are offered for improving the employee engagement.

Key Word: Engaged Employees, Core Values, Optimistic Attitude, Effective Supervisor, Career Development.

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Introduction:

In The concept Employee Engagement is relatively new for HRM and appeared in the literatures for nearly two decades (Rafferty, Maben, West and Robinson, 2005; Melcrum

Publishing, 2005; Ellis and Sorensen, 2007). The construct, employee engagement emanates from two concepts that have won academic recognition and have been the subjects of empirical research- commitment and Organizational Citizen Behaviour (OCB) (Robinson, Perryman and Hayday, 2004; Rafferty et al., 2005). Employee engagement has similarities to and overlaps with the above two concepts. Robinson et al. (2004) state that neither commitment nor OCB reflect sufficiently two aspects of engagement-its two-way nature, and the extent to which engaged employees are expected to have an element of business awareness, even though it appears that engagement overlaps with the two concepts. Rafferty et al (2005) also distinguish employee engagement and the two prior concepts- Commitment and OCB; on the ground that engagement clearly demonstrates that it is a two-way mutual process between the employee and the organization.

Employee Engagement:

Employee engagement can be described as: "The degree to which an employee is emotionally bonded to his/her organisation and is passionate about the work that really matters". The organization must work to develop and nurture engagement, which requires a two-way relationship between employer and employee. Thus Employee engagement is a barometer that determines the association of a person within the organization Engagement can also be defined as "the extent to which people enjoy and believe in what they do and feel valued for doing it."

Lockwood, (2007) defined as Employee engagement can be considered as cognitive, emotional and behavioral. Cognitive engagement refers to employees' beliefs about the company, its leaders and the workplace culture. The emotional aspect is how employees feel about the company, the leaders and their colleagues. The behavioral factor is the value added component reflected in the amount of effort employees put into their work.

Mone and London (2010) defined employee engagement is "a condition of employee who feels involved, committed, passionate, and empowered and demonstrates

those feelings in work behavior". It is thus the level of commitment and involvement an employee has towards their organization and its values.

Employee commitment and engagement is measured by three primary behaviours -

Say, Stay and Strive.

'Say' is evidently achieved if the employee consistently speaks positively about the organisation to co-workers and refers potential employees and customers.

'Stay' refers to the employee's intensive desire to be a member of the organisation, despite opportunities to work elsewhere.

'Strive' indicates an extra effort and behaviours that contribute to business success.

Categories of Employee Engagement:

According to the Gallup, the Consulting organization there is three different types of people:-

1 **Engaged:** "Engaged" employees are builders. They want to know the desired expectations for their role so that they can meet and exceed them. They are naturally curious about their company and their place in it. They perform at consistently high levels. They want to use their talents and strengths at work every day. They work with passion and they drive innovation and move their organization forward.

2. **Not Engaged:** "Not-engaged" employees tend to concentrate on tasks rather than the goals and outcomes they are expected to accomplish. They want to be told what to do just so they can do it and say they have finished. They focus on accomplishing tasks vs. achieving an outcome. Employees who are not-engaged tend to feel their contributions are being overlooked, and their potential is not being tapped. They often feel this way because they don't have productive relationships with their managers or with their coworkers.

3 **Actively Disengaged:** The "Actively Disengaged" employees are the "cave dwellers." They are "Consistently against Virtually Everything." They're not just unhappy at work;

they're busy acting out their unhappiness. They sow seeds of negativity at every opportunity. Every day, actively disengaged workers undermine what their engaged coworkers accomplish.

As workers increasingly rely on each other to generate products and services, the problems and tensions that are fostered by actively disengaged workers can cause great damage to an organization's functioning.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Employee engagement has emerged as a popular organizational concept in recent years, particularly among practitioner audiences (Saks, 2006; Bakker and Schaufeli, 2008). Practitioners and academics tend to agree that the consequences of employee engagement are positive (Saks 2006). There is a general belief that there is a connection between employee engagement and business results; a meta-analysis conducted by Harter *et al* (2002:272) confirms this connection. They concluded that, "...employee satisfaction and engagement are related to meaningful business outcomes at a magnitude that is important to many organisations".

Employee engagement is a complex, broad construct that subsumes many well researched ideas such as commitment, satisfaction, loyalty and extra role behavior. An engaged employee extends themselves to meet the organization's needs, takes initiative, reinforces and supports the organization's culture and values, stays focused and vigilant, and believes he/she can make a difference (Macey, 2006). According to Brown (2006) viewed engagement as a progressive combination of satisfaction, motivation, commitment and advocacy resulting from employees' movement up the engagement pyramid. According to Maslach *et al.* (2001), six areas of work-life lead to either burnout or engagement: workload, control, rewards and recognition, community and social support, perceived fairness and values. They argue that job engagement is associated with a sustainable workload, feelings of choice and control, appropriate recognition and reward, a supportive work community, fairness and justice and meaningful and valued work. Like burnout, engagement is expected to mediate the link

between these six work-life factors and various work outcomes.

Truss *et al* (2006) found that group in the public sector had a more negative experience of work, they reported more bullying and harassment than those in the private sector, and were less satisfied with the opportunities they had to use their abilities. This reinforces the findings of previous studies and underlines the scale of the challenge facing public sector managers in particular, and the negative impact that bullying and harassment have on employees and their levels of engagement (Emmott 2006), and According to Penna research report (2007) meaning at work has the potential to be valuable way of bringing employers and employees closer together to the benefit of both where employees experience a sense of community, the space to be themselves and the opportunity to make a contribution, they find meaning. Employees want to work in the organizations in which they find meaning at work. For Seijts and Crim (2006), employee engagement means a person who is fully involved in, and enthusiastic about, his or her work. Engaged employees care about the future of the company and are willing to invest the discretionary effort to see that the organization succeeds.

Saks (2006) argues that organisational commitment also differs from engagement in that it refers to a person's attitude and attachment towards their organisation, whilst it could be argued that engagement is not merely an attitude; it is the degree to which an individual is attentive to their work and absorbed in the performance of their role. In addition, while OCB involves voluntary and informal behaviours that can help co-workers and the organization, the focus of engagement is one's formal role performance rather than purely extra-role and voluntary behavior. According to Ketter, (2008) the corporate executives are consistently ranking the development of an engaged workforce as an organizational priority further, employee engagement can be a deciding factor for organizational effectiveness. Not only does engagement have the potential to significantly affect employee retention, productivity and loyalty, it is also a key link to customer satisfaction, company reputation and

overall stakeholder value. Thus, to gain a competitive edge, organizations are turning to HR to set the agenda for employee engagement and commitment.

According to Blessing White (2006) study has found that almost two third's (60%) of the surveyed employees want more opportunities to grow forward to remain satisfied in their jobs. Strong manager-employee relationship is a crucial ingredient in the employee engagement and retention formula. The Towers Perrin Talent Report (2003) identifies the top ten work place attributes which will result in employee engagement. The top three among the ten drivers listed by Perrin are: Senior management's interest in employees' well-being, Challenging work and Decision making authority. Vance (2006) explains the fact that employee engagement is inextricably linked with employer practices.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The objectives of this study are:

- To examine the opinion of employees about employee engagement.
- To determine, predominant factors in the perception of employees possessing the incidental influence over employee engagement.
- To put forth certain conclusions based on the findings that have been arrived.

HYPOTHESIS:

The study is conducted by applying the following hypothesis:

Null hypothesis: There are no predominant factors of employee engagement in the organization.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The study is carried out through primary and secondary data. The primary data are collected through survey method. The primary data were collected with support of standard questionnaire of the **Gallup's study**; a twelve-question survey that identifies strong feelings of employee engagement in the organization. The data collected from the respondents is through convenient sampling, from the employees of various engineering industries, in Vijayawada. Sample size is limited to 80. The Secondary data are collected from Journals, Magazines, Publications, Periodicals, Articles, Research Papers, Websites, and Manuals.

Table-1 depicts that 41 per cent are belongs to the age group of 46-55 years, and 60 per cent are having professional qualification, and 81 per cent are married, and mostly 34 per cent people are drawing salary more than Rs. 35,000/- per month, and 50 percent of the respondents are having the periodicity of 5 Years and above in the current position, and nearly 30 per cent of the respondents are having 16-20 years of total experience in their fields.

Factors Analysis – Employee engagement

The employee engagement variable consist of fourteen sub-variables in Likert's 5 point scale which ranges from strongly agree to strongly disagree. The application of factor analysis over these fourteen variables derived the following results:

Table-1: Socio Economic Profile of the Respondents

	N	%		N	%
Age			Marital Status		
Below 35 Years	18	23	Married	65	81
36-45 Years	12	15	Single	15	19
46-55 Years	33	41	Salary Drawn		
56 and Above	17	21	Rs. < 10,000	12	15
Academic qualification			Rs. 10,000 to Rs. 25,000	18	22
Professional	48	60	Rs. 25,000 to Rs. 35,000	23	29
Postgraduate	20	25	Above Rs. 35,000	27	34
Graduate	5	6	Total Work Experience		
others	7	9	Below 5 Years	10	13

Periodicity of the current position			5-10 Years	16	20
< 1 Year	11	14	11-15 Years	13	16
1-2 Years	13	16	16-20 Years	24	30
3-4 Years	16	20	Above 20 Years	17	21
5 Years and Above	40	50			

Source: Primary data

Table-2 KMO and Bartlett's Test relating to employee engagement		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.587
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	256.846
	df	91
	Sig.	.000

From the above table -2, it is found that KMO value 0.587 and Bartlett's test of Sphericity with approximate Chi-Square value 256.846 are statistically significant at 5% level. It denotes the sample is adequate to represent the factors of employee engagement. The fourteen variables obtain considerable variance to represent as motivates of employee engagement.

The following communality table indicates the range of variance exhibiting by fourteen variables of employee engagement. From the table-3, it is found that the variance ranges from 0.519 to 0.770. It denotes the variance of the

variable ranges from 51.9% to 77%. This variance designates the formation of significant factors.

The table-4, total variance table indicates the individual and cumulative variance of the derived factors. In the table-4, it is found that the fourteen factors are reduced into six predominant factors with individual variance 13.714, 10.717, 10.386, 10.117, 9.345, 9.295 and cumulative variance is 63.575. These variances are significant to individually considering derived factors.

Table-3 Communalities

No	components	Initial	Extraction
1.	Do you know what is expected of you at work?	1.000	.747
2.	Do you have the materials and equipment you need to do your work right?	1.000	.573
3.	At work, do you have the opportunity to do what you do best every day?	1.000	.625
4.	In the last seven days, have you received recognition or praise for doing good work?	1.000	.579
5.	Does your supervisor, or someone at work, seem to care about you as a person?	1.000	.646
6.	Is there someone at work who encourages your development?	1.000	.535
7.	At work, do your opinions seem to count?	1.000	.699
8.	Does the mission/purpose of your company make you feel your job is important?	1.000	.569
9.	Are your associates (fellow employees) committed to doing quality work?	1.000	.770
10.	Do you have a best friend at work?	1.000	.519
11.	In the last six months, has someone at work talked to you about your progress?	1.000	.566
12.	In the past year, have you had opportunities at work to learn and grow?	1.000	.737
13.	Intention to stay with one's employer.	1.000	.731
14.	Does you satisfied with your job	1.000	.604

Table-4 Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigen values			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.255	16.106	16.106	1.920	13.714	13.714
2	1.777	12.690	28.797	1.500	10.717	24.432
3	1.379	9.851	38.647	1.454	10.386	34.818
4	1.292	9.228	47.875	1.416	10.117	44.935
5	1.150	8.214	56.089	1.308	9.345	54.281
6	1.048	7.487	63.575	1.301	9.295	63.575
7	.822	5.868	69.443			
8	.782	5.585	75.028			
9	.746	5.326	80.355			
10	.680	4.856	85.211			
11	.598	4.271	89.482			
12	.563	4.023	93.505			
13	.491	3.510	97.015			
14	.418	2.985	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis

The following Rotated Component Matrix (a) indicates the variable composition of the factors. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization

- a. Rotation converged in 9 iterations

From the above table it is found that the first factor consist of –

- Do you have the materials and equipment you need to do your work right **(0.730)**,
- Do you have a best friend at work **(0.689)**,
- At work, do you have the opportunity to do what you do best every day **(0.668)**,

Therefore, this factor is appropriately named as **conductive work environment**.

The second factor consist of-

- Does you satisfied with your job**(0.758)**,
- Does the mission/purpose of your company make you feel your job is important **(0.618)**,

- In the last seven days, have you received recognition or praise for doing good work **(0.512)**,

Therefore, this factor is appropriately named as **optimistic attitude**.

The third factor consist of –

- At work, do your opinions seem to count **(0.819)**,
- Is there someone at work who encourages your development **(0.617)**,

Therefore, this factor is appropriately named as **effective supervisor**.

The fourth factor consist of –

- Are your associates (fellow employees) committed to doing quality work **(0.862)**,
- Intention to stay with one’s employer **(0.505)**,

Therefore, this factor is appropriately named as **core values**.

Table-5 Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Components					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
2	-.730					
10	.689					
3	.668					
14		.758				
8		.618				
4		.512				
7			.819			
6			.617			
9				.862		
13				.505		
1					.765	
5					.678	
12						-.844
11						.447

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

The fifth factor consist of one factor namely

- Do you know what is expected of you at work **(0.765)**,
- Does your supervisor, or someone at work, seem to care about you as a person **(0.678)**,

Therefore, this factor is appropriately named as **organizational relationship.**

The sixth factor consist of

- In the past year, have you had opportunities at work to learn and grow **(0.844)**,
- In the last six months, has someone at work talked to you about your progress **(0.447)**

Therefore, this factor is appropriately named as **career development.**

Factor analysis shows the five predominant factors such as **conductive work environment, optimistic attitude, effective supervisor, core values, organizational relationship, and career development** are indispensable to motivate the employees in engineering industry. In particular, conductive work climate and organizational relationship among the employees equip them in a serene and tranquil atmosphere. Superior and

subordinate relationship is highly effective in identifying the core values of the organization.

CONCLUSION:

The challenge today is not just retaining talented people, but fully engaging them, capturing their minds and hearts at each stage of their work lives.” Today, society and business are witnessing unprecedented change in terms of the global nature of work and the diversity of the workforce. Thus companies are competing for talent people who are having high performance and high competence in workplace (Berger and Berger, 2004). Organisations need employees who are flexible, innovative, willing to contribute and go ‘above and beyond the letter’ of their formal job descriptions or contracts of employment (Hartley, et al., 1995). An organization should thus recognize employees, more than any other variable, as powerful contributors to its competitive position. Engaged employees can help your organization achieve its mission, execute its strategy and generate important business results. This paper provides some noteworthy implications for practitioners. It focused on the various factors which influence employee engagement. It has been observed that organisations with higher levels of employee engagement outperform their competitors in terms of profitability. Engaged employees give their companies crucial competitive advantages—including higher productivity, customer satisfaction and lower employee turnover. The relationship between employee engagement and organizational outcomes would be stronger if better measures were used. Thus,

organisations need to better understand how different employees are affected by different factors of engagement and focus on those in order to achieve the strategic outcomes as well as to improve overall effectiveness.

Limitations and future scope of research:

Further research should be considered to gather more information regarding the employee engagement in the engineering industry. There are certain limitations of the study that must be acknowledged. First the sample selected for the study involves only the employees and there is no involvement of management representatives. Where the sample size 80 is very low, for further research, the researchers need to increase the number of respondents involved in the research study. The data collected from the respondents is through convenient sampling which restricts the generalization of findings to other groups, it is because difficulty in approaching wide variety of engineering industries in Vijayawada, due to cost and time limitation.

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